

Bayesian Model Comparison of Basis Function Systems for Particle-Reflection-Distribution Data

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Abstract

Numerical simulations for particles impinging on the first wall of fusion devices yield angle- and energy-distributions of reflected particles. Common practice is to summarize this data in extensive tables for input to plasma wall interaction codes. Our approach is to summarize the multivariate distributions by a suitable basis function system and reduce the amount of data to be stored to the coefficients of the function system under consideration. In this paper we employ MCMC within a Bayesian model comparison for calculating the evidence in order to determine which of a selection of hemispherical basis function systems performs best.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the conventional framework of plasma-wall interaction modelling, numerical tools such as SOLPS [1] and EIRENE [2] have primarily addressed the evolution of wall surfaces under ion bombardment, with a focus on sputtering as the dominant surface modification mechanism. Substantial simulations have enabled detailed characterization of the underlying atomic-scale processes, including energy- and species-dependent sputtering yields, preferential sputtering, and recoil implantation dynamics. Furthermore, the impact of surface morphology – particularly nanoscale and microscale roughness (see Fig. 1) – has been systematically investigated. While the influence of surface roughness on the reflection characteristics of incident particles is well documented, the impact of dynamically evolving surface morphology on the resulting angular and energy distributions of reflected particles has received limited analytical attention. As a result plasma simulation codes still operate by assuming perfect specular reflection for not-implanted particle. However, as can be learned from numerical simulations of ion reflection codes like SDTrimSP-2D [3], specular reflection is often strongly suppressed and the preferred direction

Figure 1: SEM-image of the surface of an EUROFER sample (2% W in Fe) under ion-irradiation with 200 eV D [4].

Figure 2: Geometry for yield reflection intensities. The D-ions are reflected into the $(\varphi-\theta)$ -polar hemisphere which is shown from a perpendicular view in the second row below. The color scale in the $(\varphi-\theta)$ -polar plots corresponds to the intensity of the reflected D-ions. In the second row (II) the target is of sinusoidal shape. It is covered by a boron layer of 20 Å thickness on bulk tungsten. The sample faces non-destructive perpendicular irradiation from the z-direction (case a, middle panel) or non-perpendicular irradiation from xz-direction with incident angle 60 deg (case b, right panel).

of reflection does not align with the mirror angle and is unexpectedly shifted towards the incident direction for non-perpendicular influx (see Fig. 2).

Central to plasma-wall interaction (PWI) simulations is the energy and angular distribution of reflected particles, expressed as $R(\varphi, \theta, E | E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S)$, which quantifies the flux of particles impinging on the wall with initial energy E_0 and incidence direction (φ_0, θ_0) and those re-entering the plasma with final energy E and exit direction (φ, θ) for a certain experimental setting S , e.g. incoming ion species or atomic composition of the wall. These distributions are computed via detailed ion reflection modeling – typically using tools such as SDTrimSP-1D [6] – which simulate the scattering of ions from surfaces with defined atomic composition. Notably, the predictions of these simulations exhibit exceptional agreement with experimental measurements. By conducting systematic parametric studies across incident energy, impact angle, ion species, and surface stoichiometry, comprehensive tables of reflection characteristics have been generated forming the basis for the PWI codes.

Separating the hemisphere into steps of three degrees of the poloidal angle θ ranging between 0 deg and 90 deg, and – accordingly – into steps of three degrees of the azimuthal angle φ ranging between 0 deg and 360 deg, one gets a mesh of the hemisphere with 3600 area portions. A typical energy of an incoming particle is in a keV range, so the reflected particles will show a broad distribution in their energy ranging from 0 eV up to a maximum of the energy of the incoming particle, so an energy mesh with up to 1000 divisions will make sense. In the end we end up with 3600 times 1000 equals 3,6 million entries to a table describing the reflection of particles resulting from a particle impact for one energy and one impact angle only. While three-dimensional distributions are impractical to be handled by tables and coarse graining possibilities are limited, a description within basis function systems, where the original data get fitted by a restricted number of orthonormal basis functions to result in a small amount of coefficients, would advantageously minimize the expense of having all the necessary information for the PWI codes available.

In the following, we introduce a suitable basis function system within a spectral framework to represent the desired reflection distributions. However, since the basis functions span both positive and negative values, even with highly accurate spectral coefficient determination, the reconstructed distribution may exhibit small, unphysical negative values. To address this issue, we initially considered intrinsically positive reconstruction schemes – such as exponentiation, absolute value, or squaring of the spectral sum. Yet, we found that a more effective and widely adopted approach is to apply a square-root transformation to the original data prior to spectral expansion. The reconstructed spectral coefficients are then used to compute the distribution, which is finally recovered by squaring the result. As we will show below, together with such a transformation comes a very helpful change from a Poisson distribution of the original data to a Gaussian distribution of the transformed data.

However, it is not obvious that a pure orthonormal basis – whether applied to the original or square-root-transformed data – provides the most compact and physically relevant representation of the reflection distribution. Given the hemispherical nature of the flux and the potential for interference or coherent effects, alternative basis systems may

offer superior description. We therefore apply Bayesian model comparison to evaluate the different basis choices.

2. MODEL FOR CONCISE DATA DESCRIPTION

To achieve a compact representation of the data, we employ a spectral approach to describe the reflected particle distributions obtained from the numerical simulations. This method effectively compresses the high-dimensional raw data – spanning a fine-grained energy grid (from zero up to the incident beam energy) and a full hemispherical angular domain – into a significantly reduced set of spectral coefficients. These coefficients encapsulate the essential features of the distribution $R(\varphi, \theta, E|E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S)$ for a given experimental configuration, serving as a condensed, low-dimensional representation of the underlying physics. Tabulating these coefficients for use in PWI codes is straightforward and computationally efficient, enabling rapid lookup and integration into PWI codes.

Given that the angular distribution of reflected ions $R(\varphi, \theta, E|E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S)$ exhibits a two-dimensional (φ, θ) -distribution on the hemisphere, we adopt an orthonormal basis system defined on the unit hemisphere — such as spherical harmonics or their hemispherical variants $H_l^m(\theta, \varphi)$ – for each discrete energy bin E . The resulting spectral coefficients $a_{lm} = a_{lm}(E)$ are then treated as functions of energy alone, enabling a hierarchical, energy-resolved decomposition of the full angular-energy distribution

$$R(\varphi, \theta, E|E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S) = \sum_{lm} a_{lm}(E) H_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad . \quad (1)$$

The hemispherical harmonics $H_l^m(\theta, \varphi)$ [7] constitute a complete orthogonal function system on the hemisphere.

$$H_l^m(\theta, \varphi) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{2} \tilde{N}_l^m \tilde{P}_l^m(\cos \theta) \cos(m\varphi) & \text{if } m > 0 \\ \tilde{N}_l^0 \tilde{P}_l^0(\cos \theta) & \text{if } m = 0 \\ \sqrt{2} \tilde{N}_l^m \tilde{P}_l^{-m}(\cos \theta) \sin(-m\varphi) & \text{if } m < 0 \end{cases} \quad , \quad (2)$$

with $\tilde{N}_l^m = \sqrt{(2l+1)(l-|m|)!/[2\pi(l+|m|)!]}$, $l \geq 0$, $m \in [-l, l]$, $\varphi \in [0, 2\pi]$, $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$, and associated Legendre polynomials $\tilde{P}_l^m(\cos \theta) = P_l^m(2 \cos \theta - 1)$.

Since the energy of the reflected particles is constrained to the interval $E \in \{0, E_0\}$, Chebyshev polynomials provide a natural choice for the spectral basis in energy space. As discussed in Chapter 5.8 of [8], these orthogonal polynomials are particularly well-suited for approximating functions on a finite interval, offering rapid convergence and excellent numerical stability.

However, since the simulation codes rely on a stochastic (Monte Carlo) framework to model the collision dynamics of incident ions with target atoms, the resulting particle distributions are inherently subject to statistical noise. While one might initially assume a Gaussian noise model, it is essential to recognize that the final reflected particle flux into the upper hemisphere is obtained by counting particles within discrete angular bins. This binning process, which involves counting individual particle events, naturally leads to a Poisson-distributed statistical uncertainty. As established in our previous work [9], the underlying statistical nature of the data is indeed Poissonian.

Due to the spectral decomposition and the presence of negative-valued components in the hemispherical basis functions, the reconstructed distribution may yield negative fit values in regions of low statistical significance, particularly where particle counts are small. However, as required by the nature of a counting experiment, values in a particle reflection distribution are strictly positive. To ensure physical consistency and positivity, we adopt a transformation strategy: instead of fitting the raw counts directly, we apply a square-root transformation to the input data. The spectral coefficients are then determined in this transformed space, and the final reconstructed distribution is obtained by squaring the result. This approach guarantees a non-negative output and has been shown to yield robust and physically meaningful reconstructions [10].

As a result, the statistical character of the input data shifts from Poissonian distribution to a Gaussian. As can be learned from Anscombe et al. [5] a transformation of the original data d_i (in our case $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $N=3600$ for every energy step) into input data y_i for the spectral approach, with

$$y_i = \sqrt{d_i + c} \quad , \quad (3)$$

converges to normally distributed input data \mathbf{y} with standard deviation $1/2$ if c is chosen to be $\frac{3}{8}$. This finding is only valid if the count value in d_i is large, which can be enforced at least for prominent parts of the reflection distribution

Figure 3: χ^2 -values as function of order K of the hemispherical basis functions;

just by running the simulation for a high number of incoming particles, (e.g. Fig. 2 results from simulating 8×10^6 projectiles). However, certain regions of the distribution inevitably exhibit very low statistical counts, e.g. at the periphery of the unit hemisphere or corresponding to particles scattered in the backward direction near the incident angle and at energies close to the beam energy. Even though such regions are typically of marginal physical interest, their influence on the spectral reconstruction must not be overlooked to avoid artifacts or erroneous conclusions.

Eventually, by applying the transformation defined in Eq. 3, we not only enforce the physical requirement of non-negativity in the reconstructed distribution but also map the underlying Poisson-distributed data into the Gaussian domain with well-established methods based on normal likelihoods, in particular when it comes to model comparison.

Taking these points together, i.e. employing the square of the fit result in order to exclude the possibility of negative fit values (due to the reduced data description of a spectral approach), and invoking Chebyshev polynomials in order to describe the energy dependence of the spectral coefficients (obtained for each data set for a certain reflection energy), we come to the following transformation of Eq. 1

$$R(\varphi, \theta, E|E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S) = \left(\sum_{lm} a_{lm}^{\text{Chebyshev}}(E) H_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \right)^2, \quad (4)$$

and employ linear regression to get the spectral coefficients for each energy E_j , with $0 \leq E_j \leq E_0$:

$$y_i = \sum_{k \in l, m}^K a_{km}(E_j) H_l^m(\theta_i, \varphi_i) \quad . \quad (5)$$

where K is the order of the hemispherical basis function needed to explain the data best within the uncertainty range of the data. For this linear regression problem we have a look at the χ^2 -value

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{y_i - \sum_{k \in l, m}^K a_{km}(E_j) H_l^m(\theta_i, \varphi_i)}{\sigma_i} \right]^2, \quad (6)$$

and invoke singular value decomposition (SVD) for each order of the hemispherical basis. Fig. 3(a) depicts values for a χ^2 -fit as function of the order of the hemispherical basis system. Approximately at higher orders than twelve the χ^2 -value drops down into overfitting, so we choose $K=12$ as the optimal order for subsequent analyses.

3. MODEL ESTIMATION VIA MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

The expectation values for the spectral coefficients a_{lm} with input data \mathbf{y} (see Eq. 3) and model M_j are

$$\langle a_{lm} \rangle = \frac{\int da_{lm} a_{lm} p(a_{lm} | \mathbf{y}, M_j)}{\int da_{lm} p(a_{lm} | \mathbf{y}, M_j)} = \frac{\int d\mathbf{a} a_{lm} p(\mathbf{a} | \mathbf{y}, M_j)}{\int d\mathbf{a} p(\mathbf{a} | \mathbf{y}, M_j)} \quad . \quad (7)$$

Figure 4: First row: (a) Reflection data of D atoms at 30 eV resulting from 100 eV D -ion beam with $\theta_0=60$ deg on the sinusoidal surface of Fig. 2 II; (b) Derived density with linear regression (c) Derived density with MCMC for the full posterior; Second row: Difference plots of (a-b), (a-c) and (b-c).

With help of Bayes theorem

$$p(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{y}, M_j) = \frac{p(\mathbf{a})p(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{a}, M_j)}{p(\mathbf{y})}, \quad (8)$$

we get

$$\langle a_{lm} \rangle = \int d\mathbf{a} a_{lm} \frac{p(\mathbf{a})p(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{a}, M_j)}{\int d\mathbf{a} p(\mathbf{a}|\mathbf{y}, M_j)}, \quad (9)$$

where the fraction term is utilized as sampling density $\rho(\mathbf{a})$ in the Markov chain Monte Carlo method. With help of the transformation of Eq. 3 the likelihood function $p(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{a}, M_k)$ is simply a Gaussian distribution with the χ^2 from above Eq. 6

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{a}, M_k) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{N}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^N \sigma_i} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}\chi^2\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{N}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^N \sigma_i} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{y_i - \sum_{k \in l,m}^K a_{lm}(E_j) H_l^m(\theta_i, \varphi_i)}{\sigma_i} \right]^2\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

To specify a prior distribution over the spectral coefficients, $p(\mathbf{a})$, we leverage the physical expectation that, when representing the data via an orthonormal spectral expansion, the coefficients should be centered near zero due to the orthogonality and cancellation properties of the basis functions. Assumed that the magnitude of the coefficients is naturally constrained by the dynamic range of the observed data, we adopt a weakly informative prior with a standard deviation on the order of the maximum observed signal, $\{\max \mathbf{y}\}$. This choice ensures that the prior remains broad enough to allow the data to dominate the inference, while still regularizing the solution against unphysical oscillations and overfitting. Therefore, with the assumption on mean value and standard deviation the appropriate probability function is a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, \{\max \mathbf{y}\})$,

$$p(\mathbf{a}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{K}{2}} \{\max \mathbf{y}\}^K} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\{\max \mathbf{y}\}^2} \sum_{lm} a_{lm}^2\right\}. \quad (11)$$

The results of the particle reflection distribution obtained via linear regression (Eq. 5) and through Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) evaluation of the posterior expectation values of the spectral coefficients are presented in Fig. 4. Both approaches yield highly consistent reconstructions, accurately capturing the structure of the reflection data. A direct comparison of the MCMC-derived and regression-based results – shown in Fig. 4(b) and (c), respectively – reveals a residual difference (b-c) that remains below 1.6×10^{-3} across the entire domain, indicating excellent agreement between the two methods and validating the robustness of the spectral reconstruction.

Figure 5: Traces of coefficient $a_{l=1,m=0}$ for 10 burn-in phases with a randomly varied (within 10% of χ^2 -result) starting value as function of MCMC-steps.

4. CHOICE OF MONTE CARLO SETTING

Due to transformation in Eq. 3 the MCMC sampling density is approximately of multidimensional Gaussian shape. Therefore, though the number of 144 MCMC variables for hemispherical basis order $K=12$ is already quite high, a fast and easy propagation of the MC variables to the extremal region of the sampling density is to be expected.

MCMC sampling is typically structured into two phases: an initial burn-in period, during which the chain converges to the target posterior distribution, followed by a sampling phase for inference. As can be seen in Fig. 5, a burn-in phase of 100 steps is sufficient to establish convergence of a sampled variable (a_{10}). Furthermore, test simulations indicate that a desired acceptance rate of approximately 0.35 – a value widely regarded as optimal for efficient exploration of high-dimensional parameter spaces with MCMC – is achieved after about 20 burn-in bins. Based on this, we set the final sampling phase to 400 steps to provide sufficient effective samples and repeat the entire MCMC procedure 10 times to ensure robustness and reproducibility (a second run of the procedure with a sampling phase of 4000 steps led to the same results within the MCMC uncertainty range). Each bin is initialized by perturbing the spectral coefficients around the linear regression result by $\pm 10\%$, ensuring diverse starting points while remaining in a physically plausible region of parameter space (as can be seen in Fig. 5 as well).

5. MODEL COMPARISON

The temptation to use only positive basis functions arises from the positivity constraint of the data. However, such systems often lack completeness and are ill-suited for spectral methods. In contrast, orthonormal bases, despite their sign-oscillatory nature, offer superior convergence and numerical stability – moreover, if a transformation like Eq. 3 is employed which ensures positivity in the final output.

We are looking for the probability of a model M_k given the data D. Employing Bayes theorem gives

$$\frac{p(M_k|D, I)}{p(M_j|D, I)} = \frac{p(M_k|I) p(D|M_k, I)}{p(M_j|I) p(D|M_j, I)} \quad (12)$$

Since no model is preferred a priori, the term with the prior model probabilities is skipped. The evidence cancels out in comparing two model probabilities obtained for the same data and we are left with the determination of the global likelihood $p(D|M_k, I)$. The integrand in Eq. (12) is mainly of Gaussian shape and can be approximated by developing its exponent around its maximum (Laplace approximation) [11].

Results for a variety of models M_j are shown in table 1. Ultimately, the evaluation via Eq. 12 yields strong support for the initial choice of the orthonormal hemispherical basis system indicated with H, which serves as the reference model. A variant omitting the constant $c = 3/8$ in Eq. 3 – which ensures no upcoming of negative values in the calculated reflection distribution – ranks second. However, the difference in model probability between "H with 3/8" and "H without 3/8" is only $\exp(-9)$, which, while numerically small, does not constitute a statistically significant preference. This is further confirmed by the fact that the posterior expectation values of the spectral

Figure 6: Values of the first 10 coefficients a_{lm} for models M_1 , M_2 and M_5 . Uncertainty ranges are smaller than the size of the circles. The x-axis labeling is: $k=1$ for $l=0, m=0$; $k=2$ for $l=1, m=-1$; $k=3$ for $l=1, m=0$; $k=4$ for $l=1, m=1$; $k=5$ for $l=2, m=-2$; $k=6$ for $l=2, m=-1$; $k=7$ for $l=2, m=0$; $k=8$ for $l=2, m=1$; $k=9$ for $l=2, m=2$; $k=10$ for $l=3, m=-3$.

j	1	2	3	4	5	6
Model M_j	H	H w/o 3/8	$\text{sgn}(H) \times H^2$	$ H $	$\text{sgn}(H) \times \sqrt{ H }$	$\sqrt{ H }$
$\log p(M_j D)$	-0.00012	-9.2	-8.0×10^5	-3.9×10^5	-1.5×10^3	-3.9×10^5

Table 1: Model comparison for models M_j given in the first row.

coefficients for both models are indistinguishable within their respective uncertainties. This agreement is visually evident in Fig. 6, which compares the first ten (out of 144) spectral coefficients for both models. The third-ranked model M_5 is defined as the square root of H multiplied by the sign of H – a hybrid construction that attempts to enforce positivity through a signed root. While the coefficients of M_5 are also plotted in Fig. 6, they exhibit substantial deviations from those of the top two models, particularly in the non-zero coefficients. Notably, though all three leading models share the same set of inactive basis functions, i.e. coefficients set to zero in Eq. 5 for $k=2,5,6,10$, yet the remaining non-zero coefficients of M_5 differ significantly in magnitude and structure, indicating a fundamentally different underlying representation. All other models yield negligible posterior probabilities and are effectively ruled out: Model M_3 with $\text{sgn}(H) \times H^2$ puts a square on the hemispherical basis just to check the possibility to describe the data by pronouncing larger values while diminishing smaller contributions in the basis functions (still a sign change in H is taken care of). Model M_4 and M_6 regard positive contributions only. Of course, for such models the transformation of Eq. 4 is superfluous and they are considered just to check the plausibility of the model comparison. A final check on the choice of the prior for the coefficients in Eq. 11 by rerunning the procedure with just setting the prior constant revealed negligibly small variations in the results only. Conclusively, the evidence strongly favors the orthonormal hemispherical basis with the Anscombe correction of Eq. 3, with only marginal differences between the top two variants, and no support for alternative constructions.

6. SUMMARY

A method for a concise description of particle reflection distributions is established by fitting coefficients of spectral approach to the particle reflection distribution function $R(\varphi, \theta, E|E_0, \varphi_0, \theta_0, S)$. To force positiveness of the result a square root/square-transformation is applied. A model comparison of variations of the spectral function identified the pure orthonormal hemispherical basis function system to perform best.

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